

CORRELATIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING EXERCISES FOR LEARNERS' COMMUNICATIVE ABILITY

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Abstract

Learners' communicative in English language has been unsatisfactory due to the factors that affect their self-confidence and motivation to speak. However, the problem persisted even though ways were used to overcome the lack of communicative ability among learners in Malaysia. Therefore, this study was conducted to address learners' perceptions of correlative language learning exercises in improving English-speaking ability. The study aimed to analyse the effectiveness of the correlative language learning exercises in motivating learners to speak in language classroom. A set of questionnaires containing two sections with 30 questions was administered. There were 50 primary school learners selected randomly to participate in this study. The results were collected and presented in the form of tables. The finding showed that self-confidence, motivation and learning environment affect the learners' English language speaking ability and the results indicated that correlative language learning exercises are able to overcome problems pertaining to communicative in language classroom. In conclusion, correlative language learning exercises improved the learners' English language speaking ability.

Keywords: Communicative, Correlative exercises, Correlative Learning, Motivation, Self-Confidence.

INTRODUCTION

The utilize of learning strategies plays a critical part and gets extraordinary considerations for a learner's life. We live in advanced period, where everybody needs something effective, successful, energetic, quick and Correlative [1]. The term 'correlative' shows up in two particular strands of instructive investigate talk: one concerning instructional method and the other concerning unused innovations in instruction. Educating learners with conventional strategy where there's as it were one way of communication is not compelling. The word 'correlative' is the key to have a compelling [2] and proficient educating and learning handle where the instructor can get learners' consideration and learners can learn more in comparison to that of the conventional strategy.

Customarily, most of the learners have been obtaining data and information through less inclusion of learners whereby learners as it were sit and tune in to the unfaltering addresses. In expansion, learners will duplicate down the unending unbelievable notes that have been composed on the whiteboard. Based on a investigate result conducted by Atiyah, El Sherbing and Guirguis [3], results appeared that the educator is the foremost prevailing individual in a classroom and the instructor is responsible for all learners. Moreover, learners as it were procuring the information but don't know how to apply it in real-life circumstances as they are not indulged in inquiry-based instruction and issue tackling. Hence, learners have less

opportunity to contribute within the lesson which is driving to unsupportive classroom environment and inactive learners.

Additionally, in Uzbekistan, the English language acts as moment a language learnt in school after Uzbek and Russian languages. Numerous of these learners confronted trouble communicating within the target language and in the long run gave up talking in English language. Learners tend to modest absent from utilizing the target language when they discover it difficult to transfer their focuses in English and they proceed to specific their thoughts by utilizing local language [4]. Thus, it influences their level of certainty to communicate in English language. On the off chance that circumstance to the like of the over continued, learners' self-confidence will fall apart, and numerous will bashful absent from communicating in English language [5]. In expansion, the restriction of learners' lexicon is one of the numerous variables that influence the learners' certainty level [6]. When learning and instructing take put, wide vocabularies are utilized in order to deliver the information. Both instructors and learners have to be have similarities in words so that they the same understanding of a discussion. Learners wavered to include themselves within the learning and instructing handle as they are not sure to share their ideas due to the need of lexicon [7]. Due to this, lessons will be influenced and restricted trade of beneficial communication to require put between learners and instructors.

In overcoming the unsupportive classroom environment and detached learners, Intelligently Language Learning Exercises (ILLE) is actualized in current language instructing because it makes a difference to move forward learners' English-speaking ability. Speaking aptitudes have to be upgraded with language exercises through intelligently learning as intelligently learning exercises give openings for change are exceedingly significance [8]. In expansion, intelligently language learning exercises empower learners to speak their considerations and concepts in numerous ways. Learners have the chance to memorize from their instructors and peers, enhance their language, process of procuring information as well as accumulate their contemplations and making consistent contemplations [9]. Hence, instructors have to be execute perfect way "the most perfect way to improve the learners" English-speaking capacity. Particularly, instructors ought to completely utilize the Correlative learning environment because it empowers learners' engagements and cooperation within the lesson that lead to dynamic learners and successful learning. Putting in intellect that Correlative classrooms are not constrained to technology-based instructing spaces alone.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Instruction nowadays has changed over time. With the ever developing of participants Z, born between 1998 and 2010, are more Web sharp compared to their group Y partners. Hence, there has been a critical require for modern instructing and learning show that suit this "Digital Natives" however penury era to investigate. The foremost critical ability in self-expression and picking up information is learners' speaking capacity [10]. The significance of talking among the learners, instructors execute an arrangement of strategies that offer assistance to lock in the learners and empowering them to talk superior. As a human being, communication plays a

crucial part in our lives. We communicate to convey messages, pass on and changing data as well as announcing things that are happening in our lives. To communicate, it isn't fundamentally to talk but you'll have it in less demanding by sending messages through the utilization of innovation. In any case, individuals got to ace talking aptitudes in arrange to communicate successfully and talking is highlighted as the major component in satisfying the target in communication [7]. In expansion, talking is said to be critical language aptitude in instruction and individual life [10]. Talking is characterized as a prepare that includes the considerations and communicating it verbally. It implies, the considerations will to begin with show up in our brain at that point as it were we express what we think [9].

In Uzbekistan, it is seen that there are a number of learners from essential schools, auxiliary school and tertiary level who are not capable in talking notwithstanding the language [11]. When the learners cannot get a handle on the fundamental aptitudes of talking at early age, it influences their execution in numerous ways. In connection to the statement stated, foreign language learners have to be secure the basic language abilities due to its significance utilization in communication [7]. The capacity to utilize and talk a world-wide language gives them nothing but benefits as they can in a roundabout way enhance their knowledge and abilities as well as help them in terms of work- shrewd; having said that, talking aptitudes have to be progressed among the learners. As learners spend most of their times in school obtaining information and improve their aptitudes, instructors and their successful educating and learning strategy play a vital role. A change learner-centred and Correlative strategy of instructing ought to be actualized in arrange to progress the learners' talking abilities [9]. Other than, he said that talking may be a learner-centred action due to the language generation exercises usage and had, in this way, proposed the authorization of intelligently instructing procedure in progressing learners' talking abilities which the center is on improving the moment language. Compared to other language aptitudes, talking is emphasized as the imperative component in accomplishing the reason of communication [8, 12-15]. With the execution of intelligently educating strategy, instructors inevitably will conduct Correlative language learning exercises to complement their strategy of instructing.

Adequate and positive situations of a classroom offer assistance the learners to memorize way better. In this manner, the capacity to be capable in a language especially depends on the environment given by the instructors, agreeing to the learners' independence. Hence, Correlative language exercises help the learners to move forward their capability [8]. Supporting the explanation, Marzuki, et al. [4] dissected that learners are barely sharing their conclusions and thought amid the talking exercises. Subsequently, the learners can move forward their talking aptitudes once the Correlative talking technique is executed. The educating technique can be changed but the finishing item ought to be centering on progressing the learners' talking aptitudes. As for that, Correlative language learning exercises help the learners in securing and utilize the language at their most extreme level. In intelligently classroom environment, it empowers learners to move around without getting settle in a certain course of action where they can maximize the classroom space. Additionally, learners are said to have the opportunity to communicate with their peers specifically and taking account their sentiments and feelings [16]. Owing to the Correlative language learning exercises, there are

various exercises that can be conducted in classroom such as inventive show, role-playing, problem-solving, discourse and gather. These exercises offer assistance the learners to share their emotions and contemplations which can be moved to the learning environment because it permits the dynamic learning and instructing. So, a few studies have been done to show that certain exercises can help students get better at speaking. Using correlative storytelling helps English learners get better at speaking and doing exercises in class. Additionally, the story doesn't stop when you finish listening to or telling it. It goes on with the students working as storytellers. They have to use their own words to tell the chosen story. So, students can improve their vocabulary by choosing the right words for their stories. Storytelling helps students speak better [17]. Moreover, it helps learners become better at speaking. Teachers and students just naturally start to communicate better. According to their study, the people they asked are getting better at asking important questions and using more advanced words. They are also getting better at telling stories and choosing the right words. Correlative storytelling also helps students get better at speaking in class.

On the other hand, drama-based exercises like act of spontaneity, playwriting and practices offer assistance to supply openings for independent utilize of unconstrained talked language in a casual setting that energizes singularity [18]. It implies that the exercises can advance talking in the event that it is centering on the learners by giving an environment where each of learners can involvement it. Moreover, these exercises inevitably can progress learners' familiarity and clarity of discourse indeed in spite of the fact that there are syntactic blunders also sentence structures mistake. The verbal input is expanded due to the reality that learners are included in both experiential and action arranged. Learners are sharp to talk on the off chance that they can relate the exercises towards their foundation information or encounters [18]. As a result, learners' have gotten to be more certain and strongwilled as well as courageous to share their suppositions and contemplations deliberately. As an entire, learners' English talking can be moved forward by utilizing Correlative language learning exercises. In any case, instructors ought to implement this strategy concurring to the learners' level of capability. In addition, teachers ought to figure out the learners' shortcomings in arrange to execute the foremost reasonable and compelling exercises for the lesson.

RESEARCH METHOD

This specific consider points to figure out the association between the issues that influence the learners' English-speaking capacity and Intelligently Language Learning Exercises (ILLE) that can be utilized as a strategy to overcome the issues in communicating within the target language. Subsequently, this think about employments quantitative strategy to examine the adequacy of the Correlative language learning exercises in propelling learners to talk in language classroom. Tis strategy appears a cause and impact relationship with numerical information and difficult truths. The comes about can be appeared in measurements, tables, charts as well as charts. Quantitative strategy may be a strategy that employments quantifiable factors and measurable methods can be utilized to examine the numbered data in instruments [19]. Thus, quantitative strategy fits this ponder the foremost because it helps the consider with clear and justifiable information.

3.1. Sampling

The analysts embraced irregular examining in this consider. Irregular inspecting is where members are chosen correspondingly [19] by choosing the tests from the full populace of the nearby essential schools in Uzbekistan. This appears that each learner undertaking essential school education has the plausibility to participate within the think about. In this way, the members have to be have the given criteria to guarantee their cooperation within the ponder is substantial. In this consider, the most points are to dissect the adequacy of intelligently language learning exercises in progressing learners' English talking and to recognize the learners' inspiration level in talking English language as the target language. There were 50 learners arbitrarily chosen as the members in add up to of (male = 20, female = 30). The age of the members, at the time of the consider, was 10 a long time ancient and they were uncovered to the neighborhood educational programs comparable to all essential schools in Uzbekistan. In expansion, the members taken an interest within the overview are deliberate.

3.2. Research instruments

In this consider, survey was utilized and was adjusted from Itayem [20]. As for the survey, Itayem [20] gives the foremost comparable survey on Correlative language learning but centering on diverse movement. So also, Likert Scale was used as an estimation to urge the information. The Likert Scale of the questions is 1 to 5 which is 1 (Strongly Agree), 2 (Agree), 3 (Neural), 4 (Disagree) and lastly 5 (Strongly Disagree). There were 30 questions in add up to for a set of surveys. The survey has two areas which are Area A and Segment B. It started with the statistic profile of the respondents in Area A and proceeded with Segment B which was their recognitions towards the exercises carried out. In area B, the questions are partitioned into three sub-topics which were 1) Self-confidence, 2) Inspiration and 3) Learning Environment. Each sub-topic contains 10 questions. Respondents replied the survey exclusively.

3.3. Data analysis

The comes about were examined by utilizing Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). In this think about, SPSS was the finest apparatus to induce numerical information and clearer comes about for the survey. By using SPSS diverse comes about that include both demographic profile and respondents' recognitions can be appeared. Subsequently, SPSS given the most excellent reply that clarified the connection between the Correlative Language Learning Exercises (ILLE) and learners' English language talking engagement. The information was examined concurring to the inquire about questions. In this think about, the discoveries were brought about to reply two inquire about questions. Two tables were constructed according to two inquire about questions with the rate of questions agreeing to Likert Scale and the mean. There were 16 questions portrayed and were dissected from the in general 30 questions to reply the two inquire about questions. The number of frequencies = n and rate = % within the two tables clarified the reactions for the survey.

4. RESULTS

To reply the primary question inquires about address, the members were required to share their discernments towards self-confidence and learning environment through Intelligently Language Learning Exercises in progressing English-speaking capacity. Table 1 appears the comes about chosen by the members. Table 1 appears distinctive comes about of participants' discernments towards self-confident and learning environment through intelligently language learning exercises in moving forward English-speaking capacity which are spoken to by the most noteworthy percentage and cruel for each category. As appeared within the table, "ILLA increases my sure to utilize English language with my friends" gotten the foremost understanding with adding up to of 82% and the cruel score is 4.22. The moment most concurred articulation by the members is "energizes me to share my thoughts amid the learning exercises" obtained 78% with the cruel score of 4.0. In expansion, 80% of the members concurred with the taking after explanation "empowers me to utilize modern lexicon amid the learning exercises" by having 3.96 of the cruel score.

Table 1: Percentage and mean results of research question 1 analysis

Question (s)	Percentage %					Mean
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Sometime	Agree	Strongly disagree	
1. ILLA increases my confidence to use English language with my friends	-	2	16	40	42	4.22
2. ILLA encourages me to share my ideas during the learning exercises	2	-	20	54	24	4.0
3. ILLA enables me to use new vocabulary during the learning exercises	-	2	18	62	18	3.96
4. I do not enjoy speaking during ILLA because I am not confident with my English language proficiency	28	30	26	12	4	2.34
5. ILLA provides a positive environment to speak English language	-	-	14	56	30	4.16
6. ILLA allows me to actively participate in the learning exercises	2	4	14	52	28	4.0
7. I find it difficult to understand the instructions for the ILLA	12	34	40	12	2	2.58
8. I fine ILLA is too distracting for me to improve me English speaking	18	50	18	12	2	2.30
9. ILLA supports my ability to engage with learning exercises in multiple ways (presentations, storytelling, group discussions, etc)	-	18	16	48	28	3.96

In any case, with the cruel score of 2.34, 58% of the members oppose this idea that they don't appreciate talking amid ILLA because they don't feel certain with their English language capability. Persistently, the members profoundly concurred on "ILLA gives a positive environment to talk English language". It can be seen by 86% of them concurred on the articulation and went with the cruel score of 4.16. Besides, they concurred that ILLA allows them to effectively take an interest within the learning exercises. The expressed articulation procured 80% understanding from the members and the cruel score is 4.0. Additionally, 76% of the members with the cruel score of 3.96 concurred by the explanation "ILLA underpins my capacity to lock in with learning exercises in numerous ways (i.e introductions, narrating, gather discourses and etc). In differentiate, 68% of the members with 2.30 of the cruel score oppose this idea that ILLA is as well diverting for them to make strides their English talking. On the other hand, to reply the moment inquire about address, the members are required to share their recognitions towards inspiration Correlative Language Learning Exercises in moving forward English-speaking capacity. Table 2 appears comes about of participants' discernments towards inspiration through Correlative language learning exercises in moving forward English language communicatively which are spoken to by the most noteworthy rate and cruel for each category.

Table 2. Percentage and mean results of research question 2 analysis

Question (s)	Percentage %					Mean
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Sometime	Agree	Strongly disagree	
1. ILLA motivates me to participate in the learning exercises	4	-	12	54	30	4.06
2. I feel proud whenever my classmates support my ideas and suggestions during the learning exercises	10	20	32	24	14	3.12
3. ILLA makes me uncomfortable to communicate with my classmates	2	2	24	46	26	3.92
4. I find it enjoyable to speak in English language during the learning exercises	24	38	22	12	4	2.34
5. It demotivates me if my classmates do not listen to my ideas and suggestions during the learning exercises	2	-	18	58	22	3.98
6. I am generally nervous if I speak incorrectly during the learning exercises	-	2	16	44	38	4.18
7. I Like to speak during ILLA because I can practice on my English speaking	6	22	22	42	8	3.24

From the Table 2 over, the members profoundly concurred on the articulation “ILLA propels me to take part within the learning exercises”. It gotten 84% assentation by the members with the cruel score of 4.06. Including to that, 50% of the members put “I like to talk amid ILLA since I can hone on my English speaking” as the moment most concurred explanation with the cruel score of 3.24. Additionally, with a cruel score of 3.12 and 8% of the members concurred that they feel glad at whatever point their classmates bolster their thoughts and recommendations amid the learning exercises. On the opposite, the negative articulation “I am by and large anxious in case I talk inaccurately amid the learning environment” gotten the most noteworthy cruel which is 4.18 and the foremost number of understanding among the members with 82%. Other than, 80% of the members and the cruel score of 3.98 agreed that ILLA demotivates them in case their classmates don't tune in to their thoughts and recommendations amid the learning exercises. Separated from that, 72% of the members did not discover it agreeable to talk in English language amid the learning exercises. As can be seen in table, the cruel scored this articulation secured 2.34. At last, 24% of the members were dubious that ILLA makes them comfortable or not to communicate with their classmates by having 3.92 of the cruel score.

5. DISCUSSION

In correlation with the study, perceptions towards correlative language learning exercises in improving English speaking, and thus answering two specific research questions, quantitative method is applied. A test was conducted to analyse the percentage and the mean of the questionnaire answered by the participants. Based on the findings, there is a significant result that aid to the improvement of English speaking. In improving English speaking communicatively, there are three important items which are analysed accordingly including self-confidence, motivation and learning environment. As for answering the first research question, how does the correlative language learning exercises aid learners in improving their English speaking, the participants came to an agreement for certain questions based on the questionnaire which was resulted in the findings. The answers were divided into two categories which are self-confidence and learning environment. Thus, the highest mean showed that correlative language learning exercises increased their confident to use English language with their friends. It was because correlative language learning exercises provide learners a positive environment to speak English language. This particular result reflected the previous study by Marzuki, Prayogo and Wahyudi [4], which stating that the learners' speaking performance improved as they are participating in correlative learning. The improvement derived from generating questions that initially to improve their self-confidence. They improved their self-confidence as they were required to formulate their own questions during the learning process.

Furthermore, the participants were highly agreed that correlative language learning exercises encouraged them to share their ideas during the learning exercises and enable them to use new vocabulary during the learning exercises. Based on their perceptions, it could be said that by sharing ideas, they naturally enhance their vocabulary usage as they need to fit in with their classmates during the implementation of the exercises. This finding is also in line with the study conducted by Marzuki, Prayogo and Wahyudi [4].

Consequently, having sufficient vocabulary during the exercises helps the learners to actively participate in the learning exercises. Learners were also seen to be able to engage with the learning exercises in various ways which lead to the improvement of their English speaking. With the exercises focus on learners' engagement with course content and learner-learner interexercise, hence, learning could be optimized [21]. In addition, the findings shown that the participants like and not reluctant to speak during the learning exercises even though not all of them may have the confidence to speak due to the positive learning environment. They felt at ease and relax to speak during correlative language learning exercises as they were not bounded to any rule that they needed to follow strictly [22]. One of the most valuable benefits of correlative tasks is the principle of collaboration which features the components of positive accountability [23]. Moreover, the participants agreed that correlative language learning exercises is the best way to improve their English speaking. However, some of them felt that the instructions used during the exercises were difficult to understand which can lead to ineffective lesson. The integration of technologies can then be viewed as a vehicle to improve learner outcomes [24].

In regard to the findings, correlative language learning exercises motivate the learners to speak in English language. As correlative language learning exercises provide positive surroundings to the learners, they felt motivated to participate in the learning exercises and thus improved their English-speaking ability. Besides, getting recognition by the classmates during the learning exercises had also motivated learners to speak. It was because they felt proud when their ideas and suggestions were accepted, and it was beneficial for them to participate in the learning exercises. They continued to share their ideas and suggestions during the learning exercises and improved their English communicatively. Furthermore, learners enjoyed speaking during the learning exercises as it allowed them to practice speaking.

Some of the learners acquired different knowledge or information throughout the learning process. Their ability to understand things were different and correlative language learning exercises provided the opportunities for the learners to put everything that they had learnt in written form to practice. Therefore, educators need to know and resolve the learners' issues and to make schools engaging places [25, 26], then they actually have to listen to what learners are saying about their classes and teachers [27-30]. By practicing, they could enhance their understanding towards the lesson learnt. On the other hand, the findings showed that correlative language learning exercises could be demotivating if the learners' opinions were being neglected by their classmates. When the learners participated in the learning exercises, they were hoping to assist their classmates in completing their tasks. However, if their ideas were rejected, they felt embarrassed and the probability for them not to speak during the discussion again was high which was not contributing to their English-speaking improvement. Study by Rusli, *et al.* [11] stated that learners were afraid of peers' judgement. It was said that learners were unlikely to speak as they wanted to avoid from showing their flaws where they could receive negative views from their classmates. Equally important, some of the learners had low motivation in speaking as they were afraid to speak incorrectly during the learning exercises.

6. CONCLUSION

As a whole, correlative language learning exercises improve learners' English-speaking ability. In correlation with the findings, participants agreed that by having self-confidence, suitable learning environment and motivation improved their English speaking communicatively. Moreover, these three factors improved through correlative language learning. Furthermore, it showed that correlative language learning exercises provide the ways to improve English speaking as learners were able to experience real conversation when they were interacting with their classmates during the learning exercises. However, some participants needed time to speak as they have had low self-confidence and it led to low motivation to speak English language. Teachers' support in conducting suitable correlative language learning exercises during English lesson is proved to be important for improving learners' English-speaking ability.

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